

SYMBIOTIC HUMAN-ROBOT FIELD OPERATIONS IN SEARCH AND RESCUE ENVIRONMENTS – CARMA*

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ABSTRACT

Current challenges in Search and Rescue (SAR) missions have evolved into highly demanding, fast-paced field deployments of First Responder (FR) teams, where multiple victims need to be detected and extricated safely and quickly in “hotzones” of increased operational complexity. Unfortunately, the technological leaps have not yet caught up with these new requirements, such as operating inside dense urban grid or in underground facilities while at the same time maintaining reliable communication links and efficient situational awareness. The EU-funded CARMA project aims to support FRs by developing a modular and intuitive platform integrating an innovative digital twin-based Command and Control (C&C) system. The solution will enable the orchestration of a set of semi-autonomous and fully autonomous Unmanned Ground Vehicles (UGV) that can work in tandem with humans. This approach will enable crucial assistance even in low-visibility environments, using innovative 3D radar-based environment mapping and analysis, with AI-enhanced victim- and threat-detection capabilities.

Keywords: Search & Rescue, First Responders, crisis management, emergency response, robot swarm.

1. INTRODUCTION

The issue of autonomy in rescue robotics is currently a very active R&D area, combining domain expertise from SAR mission planning and operational procedures together with Human-Robot Interaction (HRI) and Human-Robot Teaming (HRT). The core idea is how to make rescue robots an autonomous and collaborative “partner” within the FR team, rather than a passive technological tool for FRs to use when needed. This endeavor requires a large pool of new skills and functionalities that these robots should implement efficiently, but at the same time changes the way FR teams operate and use such assets in a completely new way within their standard operating procedures (SOP) in the various types of SAR missions.

Robotic systems are becoming an increasingly effective means of supporting or supplementing FRs in highly demanding and dangerous environments. They have been used, as remotely operated tools, in a number of events such as the collapse of the World Trade Centre in 2001, Hurricane Katrina, the 2010 earthquake in Haiti, the Deepwater Horizon oil spill, the 2011 earthquake and tsunami in Japan and numerous mining accidents. Remotely operated firefighting robots are also becoming an increasingly adopted tool for fighting complex fires such as the one that devastated Notre-Dame Cathedral in Paris, or dangerous ones in underground parking garages.

CARMA [1] aims to co-create, through a user-centered iterative methodology involving a complementary set of end-users and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) experts, as well as a

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groundbreaking, modular and intuitive platform, offering a complementary set of semi-autonomous and autonomous UGVs. These robots will be capable of working in symbiosis with humans to support and supplement FRs and assist victims in a wide range of disaster situations, including those with very low visibility.

The project will build on the most advanced research results, including those from the INTREPID project [2] in the field of disaster/rescue robotics, making them autonomous thanks to novel 3D radar-based environment mapping and analysis, combined with Artificial Intelligence (AI) for enhanced path and mission planning, as well as victim and threat detection. Symbiotic operations and natural HRI will be made possible by exploiting Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN) for collaborative tasks, Natural Language Processing (NLP), and eXtended/augmented reality (XR/AR) technologies.

Coordinated by a large European industrial leader in the crisis management domain, the CARMA consortium includes world-class research centers in the domain of AI and Social Robotics, robotics manufacturers, professional and volunteer first responders, as well as local authorities. It is complemented by an international Advisory Board and an Open Community to ensure openness and diversity. Social, ethical and legal constraints will be carefully considered during the project's lifetime. In order to prepare the ground for broad adoption and successful exploitation of the project's results, CARMA will implement an ambitious communication and dissemination plan, an engaging training curriculum, and produce a white book proposing recommendations for doctrine changes to involve the proposed solution in crisis management operations.

The following sections describe the overall methodology and the work plan implemented by the CARMA project, primarily in relation to evaluation and field testing activities.

2. METHODOLOGY – DESCRIPTION OF WORK

There are three main pillars in the concept of CARMA platform:

- **Safer reconnaissance & skill supplementation:** CARMA introduces the concept of smart symbiotic UGVs that can work in either remotely controlled, semi-autonomous, or fully autonomous mode according to the situation, in nearly all hazardous environments including those full of smoke, not yet secured or too dangerous for first responders.
- **Symbiotic Human-Robot Operations (HRO):** CARMA will make it possible to simultaneously engage several UGVs, according to the complexity and scale of the operations, and exploit their complementary set of capabilities and skills.
- **Open platform for trustable and sustainable involvement of UGVs in disaster response:** CARMA will use AI and XR technologies to enable natural interaction and control of its UGVs from a C&C system available as a portable XR/AR system or a more traditional version for command vehicle and crisis management centres.

In order to reach these objectives, the CARMA Platform will rely on an open architecture that enables both remote and on-scene operations with CARMA UGVs designed to explore the hazardous environment and perform tasks. At the same time, it will enable the FRs to remain at safe distance and assess the situation remotely either in the field, in a command truck or in a crisis management centre, using the CARMA C&C system.

Figure 1. The CARMA Platform architecture: modular and open, for multiple SAR mission types.

CARMA proposes generic and hazard-resilient, multi-sensing navigation modules to facilitate the integration of new UGVs and leveraging all the innovations of the CARMA platform, such as autonomous navigation in hazardous environments. A **Synergistic Operation Infrastructure (SOI)** enables remote connections and on-scene operations. A groundbreaking **FR-robot XR- and AI-powered interface**, which can be mounted on any UGV enables the on-site or remote commanding of the UGV and exploitation of its skills. Moreover, this interface also enables to remotely communicate with the victim, while the novel AI-powered algorithms enable a first assessment of the status of the victim.

The autonomous and semi-autonomous collaboration between robot-with-robot and FR-with-robot is achieved thanks to the **Symbiotic Mission Orchestration (SMO)** tool, which benefits from the “hybrid” team collaboration, selecting and proposing the most relevant UGV and its skills supplementation to foster more efficient and safer operations in hazardous and perilous environments. Finally, CARMA proposes a **Doctrine Authoring Tool (DAT)**, enabling the FR organizations to create their own “doctrine” of Standard Operational Procedures (SOP) [3,4], defining the deployment rules and potential collaboration scenarios between FRs and autonomous UGV.

There are three main types of state-of-the-art UGVs included in the CARMA platform, which will be enhanced and improved towards making them semi- and fully-autonomous:

- **NEO HD**: Modular, agile, rugged, with flippers, goes through opening of 40cm width, climb stairs, arm enabling remote manipulations including in the case of CBRN incidents.
- **TEC 800**: Modular powerful rugged robotic platform with carrying and manual fire extinction skills supplementations.
- **Anymal**: Quadruped robot with high mobility, capable to explore challenging cluttered environments.

Figure 2. The three UGVs included in the CARMA Platform (top-left: Neo HD; top-right: TEC 800; bottom: Anymal).

3. PILOTING EVENTS – FIELD TRIALS

Evaluating CARMA results on a regular basis is crucial to ensure the effectiveness and efficiency of its results and their adoption by end-users and acceptance by citizens. The CARMA project will evaluate the effectiveness and acceptance of the proposed platform in the frame of **four pilots** in complementary operational environments:

- **Pilot 1 / CBRN-E incident in a public space:** The pilot will take place in the Integral Security and Emergency Training Centre (CIFSE) of the Security, Emergency and Mobility Corps and Services of the city of Madrid, Spain.
- **Pilot 2 / USAR mission deployment:** Urban area impacted by an earthquake with collapsed buildings, taking place at HRTA's Afidnes Training Center (ATC) in Athens, Greece.
- **Pilot 3 / Underground Parking Garage Fire:** A fire breaks in the "Meyerbeer-Opéra" underground car park in the centre of Paris, France.
- **Pilot 4 / Cargo incident impacting Marseille Grand Port:** An explosion occurs on a ship docked at the Grand Port, the biggest French port, where the training centre of BMPM is located in Marseille, France.

4. CONCLUSIONS

CARMA envisions a new, symbiotic collaboration between FRs and robotic technologies, aiming at the augmenting the FR team with “partners” of supplementary skills and capabilities, rather than simply extending the existing toolkits of UGVs and other robotic platforms already in operational use today. The project started officially on September 2024 and it will evolve in a period of 36 months.

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